

GAFUR GHULAM WAS SKILLFUL POETRY OF XX CENTURY

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Annotation: In this article, you will see the theoretical analysis of the work of Ghafur Ghulam, a great writer, poet and skilled translator of our people, and his entry into poetry and the field of literature in general.

Key words: Literature, writer, poet, translator, poetry, short stories, Shum bola, Yadgor, Sen yetim emassan, Sog'inish, Kuzatish

Gafur Ghulam was a poet and writer who was able to listen to the heart of our people and feel the pain of people. Having been orphaned by his parents since his youth, young Gafur Ghulam takes care of his siblings. For this reason, he is forced to do various things. Since he studied at school and is literate, he also works as a typist in a printing house, thereby entering literature. He works and learns at the same time. While working at the printing house, he studied various literary courses. Later, he improved his knowledge at the Tashkent Pedagogical Institute and immersed himself in literature. He imparts his knowledge to students in various educational institutions in his field. During his career, he writes various stories and poems, based on the situation at that time. Gafur Ghulam skillfully translated the works of Pushkin, Lermontov, Nizami Mayakovsky, Shakespeare, Dante and other writers and poets into Uzbek. The translator says about the importance of the works of Vladimir Mayakovsky in the expansion of his thinking and the formation of his artistic taste: "I know and love Russian classical artists. I translated many of their works into my native language. But "I want to say that I am Mayakovsky's student" opened up the most exciting and unlimited possibilities for me in the areas of weight, vocabulary, and the melodic structure of symbolic poetry. In addition to anger in Mayakovsky's satire, critical sarcasm, and the power of joyful emotion in his lyrics, I tried to gather in myself the bold eloquence of his methods, the courage of metaphors, and expressiveness of exaggerations. I even had to use the methodical, melodious and meaningful construction of poetry in the Uzbek poetry system."

The main part of Gafur Ghulam's works is autobiographical, and the person who reads them feels as if Gafur Ghulam's youth was in the past war years. For

example, the story "Mening o'g'rigina bolam" tells about the writer's own life. It reveals the effects and damages of the war on the people. The image of a father who sent his son to war is highlighted in the poem "Sog'inish". The verses of the poem describe the restless heart of the Father, who is waiting for some good news from his son who went to war. As they say, the imagination is faster than anything else, the father's heart is sometimes frightened by panic, the hundreds of "sighs" that come around every day can cause these panics, and it is expressed through the lines "No matter what my father does, it's an inherited feeling...". When studying the works of Gafur Ghulam in the classical poetic genre, it can be seen that the artistic laws in them are kept in their place, and the expressive shell, formal units and features of the pictorial method fully preserve the classical traditions. Academic poet Gafur Ghulam has created a rich work in the stories and short stories of the epic type, and in the lyrical type, he has created free and finger-weight poems, epics, ghazals, mukhamas and masnaavis belonging to the "Universal lyrics" gained fame in his time. Also, a number of scientific and sharp journalistic articles, aphorisms, satires and humorous anecdotes full of humor were inherited from the sensitive poet as intellectual property. Gafur Ghulam says in one of his wisdoms from Yondaftar: "The fate of a particle is older than the Sun." Even the smallest meaning in the poet's works is connected with the long past of the ancient Turkish people. The ghazals, muhammas, and masnavis with an auspicious tone in his works highlight the artistic thinking, symbolic and visual elements of folklorism, which prove the connection of the poet's work with our classical literature and folk art with a thousand-year history. As mentioned, Gafur Ghulam's childhood coincided with the war, and at that time the men of every household were taken to the war, and women and children suffered from hunger, and the streets were full of beggars and hungry children. Writer grew up seeing all this with his own eyes, and later took a pen in hand to write his memories. At this time, the story "Shum bola" was born. The main character of "Shum Bola" is a 14-year-old orphan boy. His mother works tirelessly for her children from morning to night, and Qoravoy does not stop playing with his friends on the street. He was one of those restless children who would turn blue if he hit the ground, and his heart would tighten if he stayed in one place for too long. Disappointing his mother, he goes on the road to earn money for a living, thus his adventure in Tashkent begins and this adventure lasts one and a half years. No matter where Qoravoy goes, no matter who he flies with, adults look at him rudely and treat him rudely. Various people pretending to caress the orphan's head try to take advantage of it. It's okay,

there are people who lead this young child down various crooked paths. For example, Eshan, who is a guide to hundreds of people and mentions God in every word, directly invites Qoravoy to steal. In this story, the "lie" used by Qoravoy in slandering Sariboy Bolis shows that the author effectively used the ancient Eastern fairy tale "Uch yolg'ondan qirq yolg'on" as a source of artistic nourishment in this work. At the same time, elements of folklorism were fully manifested in the light humor, anecdotes and stories of the poet's works, and in the image of Nasriddin Efendi. describes the environment through the eyes of a young child, full of colorful content. During this story, I was repeatedly convinced of Qoravoy's ingenuity, promptness and ability to get out of any situation safely.

During his life, the writer and poet lived only by work and creativity. In 1943, due to his work, he was elected a full member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In the poems of the poet, the poet tries to find answers to the questions of the peace period, to show the successes of the Uzbek people in their labor activities. The hero of his works is an ex-soldier busy with world affairs and peaceful work. We can call Gafur Ghulam an enthusiastic singer of peace, friendship and people's happiness. Since Gafur Ghulam's work has taken a place in the hearts of our people, young and old are still lovingly reading his books and works. So, the weighty, genre diversity in the lyrics of the academic poet Gafur Gulom served as an artistic shell delivering the main idea and content. The poet's works reflect oriental wisdom, loyalty to the truth, folk light rhythm and melody, and the artistic image that can be understood from the comic scene.

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